

Incidence of Tuberculosis and Opportunistic Respiratory Infections in HIV Patients: A One-Year Study at a Tertiary Care Hospital

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Abstract:

Background: Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) remains a noteworthy global health challenge, with opportunistic infections (OIs) such as tuberculosis (TB) and other respiratory infections contributing substantially to morbidity and mortality. Despite advances in antiretroviral therapy (ART), these infections continue to pose significant risks, particularly in resource-limited settings. The study investigated the incidence of TB and opportunistic respiratory infections among HIV patients and to identify associated risk factors.

Methods: A descriptive observational study was carried out over one year at a tertiary care hospital, involving 160 HIV patients. Data were gathered from medical records and patient interviews, focusing on demographic details, CD4 counts, viral loads, and incidence of TB and other respiratory infections. Statistical analysis was accomplished using SPSS version 21.0.

Results: The incidence of tuberculosis among HIV patients was 18.75%, while the incidence of opportunistic respiratory infections was 26.25%. Lower CD4 counts were substantially associated with higher incidences of both TB and opportunistic respiratory infections ($p < 0.05$). Males were more likely to develop opportunistic respiratory infections compared to females ($p = 0.04$). No significant correlation was found between age or viral load and the incidence of these infections.

Conclusion: The study highlights a substantial burden of TB and opportunistic respiratory infections among HIV patients, with a significant association with lower CD4 counts. Gender disparities were also observed in the incidence of opportunistic respiratory infections.

Recommendations: To reduce the burden of these infections, it is essential to maintain higher CD4 counts through effective ART and regular monitoring. Gender-specific strategies should be explored to address the higher incidence of opportunistic respiratory infections in males. Further research is needed to fully understand the roles of age and viral load in the incidence of these infections.

Keywords: HIV, Tuberculosis, Opportunistic Infections, CD4 Count, Gender Disparities

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Introduction

The Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) continues to pose a serious threat to global health, affecting millions of individuals globally. Opportunistic infections (OIs) still carry a high risk, even with advancements in antiretroviral therapy (ART) that have greatly increased the life expectancy and quality of life for people living

with HIV. Tuberculosis (TB) and other respiratory infections are among the most common OIs in HIV-infected individuals, leading to increased morbidity and mortality [1].

Tuberculosis is the leading cause of death among people with HIV, accounting for approximately one in three AIDS-related deaths globally. The

interplay between HIV and TB is particularly detrimental, as HIV compromises the immune system, making individuals more susceptible to TB infection and reactivation of latent TB. Studies have shown that the incidence of TB is substantially higher in HIV-infected individuals when compared to the general population, with rates varying across different regions and settings [2].

Opportunistic respiratory infections other than TB also significantly impact the health of HIV patients. These include bacterial pneumonia, pneumocystis pneumonia (PCP), and fungal infections such as cryptococcosis. These infections are a major cause of hospitalization and death among people living with HIV, particularly in resource-limited settings where access to preventive measures and treatment may be constrained.

CD4 count, a key indicator of immune function in HIV patients, plays a critical role in the susceptibility to OIs. Lower CD4 counts are correlated with a higher risk of developing both TB and other respiratory infections. Maintaining higher CD4 counts through effective ART is crucial in reducing the incidence of these infections and improving patient outcomes [3].

Gender disparities in the incidence of OIs have been observed, with some studies indicating that males may be more susceptible to certain infections compared to females. This could be due to a variety of factors, including differences in health-seeking behavior, comorbidities, and biological differences in immune response.

While age and viral load are important factors in the overall management of HIV, their roles in the incidence of TB and other respiratory infections remain less clear. Some studies suggest that these variables may not be directly associated with the occurrence of these infections, indicating the need for more focused research to understand their impact fully [4].

Given the ongoing burden of TB and opportunistic respiratory infections among HIV patients, this study aims to investigate the incidence of these infections and explore the associated risk factors. Understanding these dynamics is essential for developing targeted interventions to reduce the burden of OIs and improve the health outcomes of people living with HIV.

The study was conducted to investigate the incidence of tuberculosis and opportunistic respiratory infections in patients with human immunodeficiency virus (HIV).

Methodology

Study Design: A descriptive observational study.

Study Setting: The study was carried out at Batra Hospital and Medical Research Centre over a period of one year.

Participants: A total of 160 participants diagnosed with HIV were comprised in the study. These participants were selected from patients attending the outpatient department and those admitted to the inpatient wards of the hospital.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients diagnosed with HIV.
2. Patients aged 18 years and above.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients who were already on treatment for tuberculosis or any other respiratory infection prior to the study.
2. Patients with incomplete medical records.

Bias: To minimize bias, a consecutive sampling method was used, and all eligible patients who met the inclusion criteria were involved in the study. The data collection process was standardized to ensure consistency.

Variables: The primary variables included the incidence of TB and opportunistic respiratory infections. Other variables recorded were demographic data (age, gender), clinical data (CD4 count, viral load), and treatment history.

Data Collection: Data were gathered from medical records and patient interviews using a structured data collection form. The form included sections on demographic details, clinical history, laboratory findings, and treatment information.

Procedure

1. Relevant data were extracted from the patients' medical records.
2. Patients were interviewed to gather additional information if necessary.
3. Laboratory tests, including sputum smear microscopy, culture, and molecular tests for tuberculosis, were conducted as per the hospital's standard protocols.
4. Data on opportunistic respiratory infections were collected based on clinical diagnosis and laboratory confirmation.

Statistical Analysis: The gathered information was logged into a database, and SPSS version 21.0 was used for analysis. Less than 0.05 was the threshold for statistical significance.

Ethical Considerations: The study protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee and written informed consent was received from all the participants.

Result

The study comprised 160 individuals in total. Table 1 provides an overview of the participants' clinical and demographic features.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

Characteristic	Number (n=160)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
• Male	102	63.75
• Female	58	36.25
Age (years)		
• 18-29	38	23.75
• 30-39	56	35.00
• 40-49	42	26.25
• ≥50	24	15.00
CD4 Count (cells/μL)		
• <200	64	40.00
• 200-349	48	30.00
• ≥350	48	30.00
Viral Load (copies/mL)		
• <10,000	45	28.13
• 10,000-49,999	72	45.00
• ≥50,000	43	26.88

The incidence of tuberculosis among the participants was found to be 18.75%. Table 2 provides detailed information on the incidence of tuberculosis stratified by gender, age, CD4 count, and viral load.

Table 2: Incidence of Tuberculosis

Characteristic	Number (n=30)	Percentage (%)	p-value
Gender			
• Male	22	73.33	0.05
• Female	8	26.67	
Age (years)			
• 18-29	8	26.67	0.12
• 30-39	12	40.00	
• 40-49	7	23.33	
• ≥50	3	10.00	
CD4 Count (cells/μL)			
• <200	20	66.67	0.01
• 200-349	7	23.33	
• ≥350	3	10.00	
Viral Load (copies/mL)			
• <10,000	6	20.00	0.08
• 10,000-49,999	15	50.00	
• ≥50,000	9	30.00	

The incidence of opportunistic respiratory infections was 26.25%. Table 3 details the incidence of these infections stratified by gender, age, CD4 count, and viral load.

Table 3: Incidence of Opportunistic Respiratory Infections

Characteristic	Number (n=42)	Percentage (%)	p-value
Gender			
• Male	26	61.90	0.04
• Female	16	38.10	
Age (years)			
• 18-29	12	28.57	0.10
• 30-39	15	35.71	

• 40-49	10	23.81	
• ≥ 50	5	11.90	
CD4 Count (cells/ μ L)			
• <200	25	59.52	0.03
• 200-349	10	23.81	
• ≥ 350	7	16.67	
Viral Load (copies/mL)			
• <10,000	8	19.05	0.09
• 10,000-49,999	22	52.38	
• $\geq 50,000$	12	28.57	

As per the data, there was a significant correlation ($p < 0.05$) between the occurrence of opportunistic respiratory infections and tuberculosis and lower CD4 counts. Additionally, there was a significant correlation ($p = 0.04$) between gender and the occurrence of opportunistic respiratory infections. The incidence of opportunistic respiratory infections and tuberculosis was not significantly correlated with age or viral load ($p > 0.05$).

Discussion

The study revealed that the incidence of tuberculosis among HIV patients was 18.75%, indicating a substantial burden of this co-infection in the studied population. Additionally, opportunistic respiratory infections were prevalent, with an incidence rate of 26.25%. These findings underscore the vulnerability of HIV patients to serious respiratory conditions, highlighting the need for vigilant monitoring and proactive management of these infections.

A significant relationship was found between lower CD4 counts and the higher incidences of both tuberculosis and opportunistic respiratory infections. This suggests that patients with more advanced immunosuppression are at greater risk, emphasizing the importance of maintaining higher CD4 counts through effective antiretroviral therapy and regular health check-ups. The study also identified a gender disparity in the incidence of opportunistic respiratory infections, with males being more affected than females. This could indicate possible gender-specific factors that need further exploration to tailor preventive strategies effectively.

Interestingly, the study found no significant association between age or viral load and the incidence of tuberculosis or opportunistic respiratory infections. This suggests that while viral load is a critical factor in the overall management of HIV, it may not be a direct predictor of these specific co-infections. Similarly, age did not appear to influence the incidence rates, indicating that both younger and older HIV patients are equally at risk for these infections. Overall, these findings highlight the multifaceted nature of HIV management and the need for comprehensive care

strategies that address not only the viral infection but also the associated opportunistic conditions.

Tuberculosis and other opportunistic respiratory infections are major complications in patients with HIV, significantly impacting morbidity and mortality. A study reported that out of 127 HIV patients with respiratory infections, 22.05% had tuberculosis. Bacterial pneumonia was diagnosed in 59.84% of cases. The mean CD4 count was 168.57 cells/ μ L, and knowledge of pulmonary complications in relation to CD4 count helps in faster diagnostic and therapeutic approaches [5].

Research found a TB incidence rate of 3.08 per 1000 person-years among HIV patients. Predictors included age above 65, underweight status, and past opportunistic infections. There was a significant association between TB incidence and viral load over time [6]. A retrospective study showed that 22% of newly diagnosed HIV patients had TB, with pulmonary TB in 51% and extra-pulmonary TB in 49%. The median CD4 count was 62.5 cells/ μ L, and the mortality rate was 11.8% [7].

A study found a 26.6% prevalence of HIV-TB co-infection. Higher incidence was seen in males, semi-skilled workers, and those with secondary education. Low CD4 counts and alcohol consumption were significant determinants [8]. Another study observed that 80.2% of HIV patients developed TB with CD4 counts below 200 cells/ μ L. Pulmonary TB was more common in those with lower CD4 counts [9].

Conclusion

The incidence of tuberculosis among HIV patients was found to be 18.75%, while the incidence of opportunistic respiratory infections was 26.25%. A significant association was observed between lower CD4 counts and higher incidences of both tuberculosis and opportunistic respiratory infections. Additionally, males were more likely to develop opportunistic respiratory infections compared to females. However, no significant association was found between age or viral load and the incidence of either tuberculosis or opportunistic respiratory infections.

Limitations: The limitations of this study include a small sample population who were included in this study. Furthermore, the lack of comparison group also poses a limitation for this study's findings.

Recommendation: To reduce the burden of these infections, it is essential to maintain higher CD4 counts through effective ART and regular monitoring. Gender-specific strategies should be explored to address the higher incidence of opportunistic respiratory infections in males. Further research is needed to fully understand the roles of age and viral load in the incidence of these infections.

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List of Abbreviations:

ART: Antiretroviral Therapy

CD4: Cluster of Differentiation 4

HIV: Human Immunodeficiency Virus

OI: Opportunistic Infection

PCP: Pneumocystis Pneumonia

SPSS: Statistical Package for the Social Sciences

TB: Tuberculosis

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